

Kinetics and mechanism of electron-transfer reactions : Oxidation of pyruvic acid by thallium(III) in acid perchlorate medium

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Manuscript received 01 September 2009, revised 04 January 2011, accepted 25 May 2011

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of pyruvic acid by thallium(III) have been studied in acid perchlorate medium. The stoichiometry of the reaction is represented by the eq. (1),

The kinetic rate law corresponds to the eq. (2),

$$\frac{-d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_h[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{CH}_3\text{COCO}(\text{OH})]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + K_h[\text{CH}_3\text{COCO}(\text{OH})]} \quad (2)$$

The oxidation product of the substrate is acetic acid. A plausible reaction mechanism accounting for experimental observations has been suggested.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, thallium(III), pyruvic acid, mechanism.

Introduction

A number of research papers has appeared on the oxidation of organic compounds with various functional groups of different reactivity towards thallium(III) in aqueous acid medium¹. This oxidant has shown a unique selectivity in such reactions more particularly the reactions where a mixture of products of oxidation of the substrate has been found. The synthetic potential of the oxidant has also been exploited in preparation of certain organo-thallium derivatives, the latter through solvolysis of carbon-thallium bond known to yield oxidation products²⁻¹¹.

Much interest in chemistry of thallium(III) has been created to know more about the role of thallium(II) but the oxidation studies reported so far have provided no unequivocal evidence of this intermediate.

Our aim of undertaking this title study is to understand whether or not the oxidation of this organic acid takes place via an intermediate complex. Secondly, it will further be interesting to probe whether or not thallium(II) has any role in the oxidation of pyruvic acid (Pyr).

Experimental

Experimental details related to the preparation and standardization of various reagents employed in this study have been provided elsewhere¹.

Kinetics experiments were carried out in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks immersed in a thermostated water bath adjusted to within ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. Reaction mixtures were prepared by mixing requisite volume proportions of desired concentrations of various reaction components such as pyruvic acid, perchloric acid and lithium perchlorate except thallium(III). When the reaction mixture attained the temperature of the thermostated water-bath, the temperature pre-equilibrated solution of thallium(III) of the desired concentration was added into the reaction mixture. The time of initiation of the reaction was recorded when half of the pipette contents were released into reaction mixture. An aliquot (5 or 10 cm³) of the reaction mixture after swirling the flask was withdrawn periodically and then added into an aqueous solution of potassium iodide (~10%), the liberated iodine was titrated against thiosulphate solution using starch

as an indicator². However, it is required that the titration should be carried out with vigorous shaking to golden-yellow end-point.

Initial rates (k_i) were computed employing plane mirror method¹³. Pseudo-first order plots were also made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Rate measurements in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

Doubly distilled water was employed throughout the study, the second distillation was from alkaline potassium permanganate solution in an all glass apparatus.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometric experiment with sufficient excess of the oxidant over the substrate were allowed to occur under kinetic conditions and the excess of thallium(III) was estimated iodometrically. The stoichiometry corresponds to the reaction as represented by eq. (1) (Table 1).

Table 1. Stoichiometric results of thallium(III)-pyruvic acid reaction

[HClO ₄] = 0.51 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 30 °C		
10 ³ [Tl ^{III}] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ [Pyr] (mol dm ⁻³)	$\frac{\Delta[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]}{\Delta[\text{Pyr}]}$
2.0	1.0	1 : 1
4.0	2.0	1 : 1
6.0	3.0	1 : 0.98
8.0	4.0	1 : 0.97
10.0	5.0	1 : 0.98

Tl⁺ was tested as thallos iodide (a yellow precipitate). The reaction mixture was neutralized by the addition of NaOH, Tl³⁺ precipitated as Tl(OH)₃ was centrifuged. Neutralized ferric chloride solution was added into the filtrate that yielded red colour confirming the presence of acetate ions in the reaction mixture¹⁴. No quantitative estimation of acetate ion was possible in the presence of other reaction components.

Results

The concentration of thallium(III) was varied in the range (1.0–5.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. Initial rates (k_i , mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) were computed and the plot of initial rate (k_i) versus [Tl^{III}] yielded a straight line passing through the

origin conforming to first order dependence with respect to the oxidant.

Similarly the concentration of pyruvic acid was varied in the concentration range (1.0–10.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively. Initial rates (k_i) were plotted against the concentration of pyruvic acid, a straight line initially passing through the origin tended towards a limiting rate at higher concentrations indicating a complete dependence with respect to pyruvic acid.

The concentration of lithium perchlorate was varied from 0.25 to 1.5 mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k , s⁻¹) were found to be independent of the concentration of lithium perchlorate ruling out any effect of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction.

The concentration of hydrogen ion was varied from 0.5 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ employing perchloric acid at $I = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³ (ionic strength (I) was adjusted by perchlorate) at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients and at 25, 30 and 35 °C respectively. The rate decreases with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion.

The concentration of chloride ion was varied employing sodium chloride at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients. The rate decreases drastically with increasing concentration of chloride ion.

The effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction was studied keeping fixed concentrations of the reaction ingredients and $I = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³ (ionic strength (I) was adjusted by lithium perchlorate) at 25, 30 and 35 °C respectively. The energy of activation was calculated to be (66 ± 2) kJ mol⁻¹.

The test of free radicals was negative as addition of acrylonitrile or acrylic acid monomer in the reaction mixture in the presence and absence of chloride ion did not indicate polymerization. Moreover, these reaction mixtures were left for more than *ca.* 2 h, no white sediment was observed.

Discussion

Thallium(III) is quite stable in solution and is reported^{15,16} to undergo hydrolysis in dilute acidic solutions as represented by eq. (2),

The hydrolysis constant (K_h) was reported to be 0.086 at 25 °C which was estimated to be 0.088 at 30 °C employing enthalpy change of hydrolysis (69.4 kJ mol⁻¹). Since the rate decreases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration, this shows that the hydrolyzed $\text{Tl}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species is more reactive than the thallic ion (Tl^{3+}) species. It is not a unique observation in thallium(III) reactions. There are a large number of such reactions where retarding effect of hydrogen ion on the rate has been assigned to the reactivity of this hydrolyzed species¹⁷. The dissociation constant¹⁸ of pyruvic acid is reported to be 3.2×10^{-3} at 25 °C. Moreover, keto acids are partially hydrated in aqueous solution. Since the hydration constant¹⁹ of pyruvic acid is of the order of $\sim 10^3$, the acid would mainly be present in the hydrated form ($\text{RC}(\text{OH})_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$).

Further the hydrated form would remain undissociated in view of $K_a \ll [\text{H}^+]$. Thus considering $\text{Tl}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ to be the reactive form, the following mechanism consisting of steps (2) to (4) can be envisaged.

The loss of thallium(III) will lead to the rate law (5) or (6)

$$\frac{-d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = \frac{kKK_h[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{Pyr}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{Pyr}]} \quad (5)$$

or

$$k' = \frac{kKK_h[\text{Pyr}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{Pyr}]} \quad (6)$$

where k' is pseudo-first order rate constant and $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{Pyr}]$ are the gross analytical concentrations of thallium(III) and free equilibrium concentration of pyruvic acid respectively.

Fig. 1. A plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{CH}_3\text{COCO}(\text{OH})]^{-1}$ in the reaction of thallium(III) and pyruvic acid: $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (O) 30 °C, (Δ) 35 °C and (\square) 40 °C.

The reciprocal of eq. (6) on re-arrangement yields eq. (7),

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+] + K_h}{kKK_h[\text{Pyr}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

A plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{Pyr}]$ was made from eq. (7) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1), k was calculated from the intercept to be $3.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30 °C.

The eq. (7) on further re-arrangement yields eq. (8),

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{kKK_h[\text{Pyr}]} + \frac{K_h}{kKK_h[\text{Pyr}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

Another plot of $1/k'$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ was made from the eq. (8) at constant concentration of pyruvic acid that also yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2). The intercept and slope of this line are represented by eqs. (9) and (10) respectively.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{1}{kKK_h[\text{Pyr}]} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\text{Int} = \frac{K_h}{kK_h[\text{Pyr}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (10)$$

From eqs. (9) and (10), eq. (11) is obtained

$$\text{Int} = (K_h \times \text{Slope}) + 1/k \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2. A plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ in the reaction of thallium(III) and pyruvic acid : $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{CH}_3\text{COCO}(\text{OH})] = 0.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{I}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (O) 25 °C, (Δ) 35 °C and (\square) 40 °C.

Let the intercept obtained in $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ plot be represented by Int_2 and that of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{Pyr}]^{-1}$ plot by Int_1 .

Thus the eq. (11) can be further re-arranged to eq. (12),

$$\text{or } K_h = (\text{Int}_2 - \text{Int}_1)/\text{Slope} \quad (12)$$

This eq. (12) was employed for calculation of hydrolytic constant ' K_h ' of thallium(III) and the values of K_h obtained at 30 and 35 °C are 0.083 ± 0.002 and 0.087 ± 0.002 in quite good agreement with the earlier reported values. The equilibrium constant for complex formation between the oxidant and substrate was determined to be (120 ± 5) and $(86 \pm 4) \text{ mol dm}^{-1}$ at 30 and 35 °C respectively.

Thermodynamic parameters such as energy of activa-

tion to be $(66 \pm 8) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ was calculated from the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ and entropy of activation was calculated in a conventional manner employing the following eq. (13) to be $(-75 \pm 8) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

$$k = e^{-\frac{k_B T}{h}} \cdot e^{-E_a^*/RT} \cdot e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R} \quad (13)$$

The large (-)ve entropy of activation corresponds to a more compact and ordered transition state.

Thallium(III) is substitution labile as the rate of water exchange for aquothallium(III) is reported^{20,21} to be $3 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Since the rate of complex formation does not depend on the nature of the incoming ligand, the rate controlling step in thallium(III) substitution reactions should be the dissociation of an aqua ligand. This is true for anation reactions where rate constant *ca.* $9 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ has been reported²² for Cl^- , Br^- , CN^- with $[\text{Tl}(\text{edta})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$. Since the observed rate constant is significantly lower than expected for substitution at $\text{Tl}_{(\text{aq})}^{3+}$, such an observation negates formation of pyruvate thallium(III) complex to be the rate determining step. Thus the reaction in all probability is redox controlled and not substitution controlled.

Nevertheless, such an intermediate complex between oxidant and the substrate is substantiated indirectly by the effect of chloride ion concentration on the rate of the reaction. Since the rate decreases with increasing concentration of chloride ion, this shows that the entry of the substrate into the co-ordination shell of the metal ion is blocked owing to pre-occupation by the chloride ions forming stronger chlorothallium(III) complexes²³.

In general the effect of chloride ion in the reactions of thallium(III) has been categorised in two ways. Their first category reactions such as the oxidation of H_3PO_2 ²⁶, H_3PO_3 ²⁷, Sb^{III} ²⁸ and Fe^{II} ²⁰ with thallium(III) exhibits enhancement in rate by chloride ions whereas reactions of second category such as As^{III} ³⁰, $\text{NH}_3 + \text{OH}^+$ ¹⁷, N_2H_5^+ ¹⁷, H_2O_2 ³¹ and almost all organic acids³² are decelerated by chloride ion.

The order of reactivity of chloro-thallium complexes in the reactions of the first category is observed to be : $\text{TlCl}_4^- > \text{TlCl}_3 > \text{TlCl}_2^+ > \text{TlCl}^{2+} > \text{Tl}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ whereas it is reversed in reactions of the second category as $\text{TlCl}_4^- < \text{TlCl}_3 < \text{TlCl}_2^+ < \text{TlCl}^{2+} < \text{Tl}(\text{OH})^{2+}$.

However, two important conclusions can be drawn

from the effect of chloride ion on the rate of the reaction in support of the reaction mechanism.

(i) First the strong chloro-thallium(III) complexes support the reactivity of $Tl(OH)^{2+}$ species as has been suggested. The decrease in hydrolysis of chloro-thallium(III) complexes will decrease the concentration of $Tl(OH)^{2+}$ species resulting further decrease in rate on increasing hydrogen ion concentration.

(ii) Secondly, since the chloride ion preferentially occupies co-ordination sites of thallium(III) to the pyruvic acid, the formation of an intermediate complex between metal ion and substrate is indirectly supported. Had it not been the situation the reaction would have occurred through redox rupturing of energetically more facile metal-substrate intermediate complex.

Thus the probable mode of electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant to account for the reaction events as in Scheme 1 can be suggested.

Scheme 1

There is also an alternative possibility based on more facile one electron transfer as compared to two electron transfer in a step. If this is the fate of the reaction events, Tl^{II} might be an intermediate reactive species of Tl^{III} .

The oxidation of Tl^I or reduction of thallium(III) is generally supposed to occur via formation of a thallium(II) transient intermediate³³.

Scheme 2

Although Scheme 2 explains kinetic features of the reaction, this was, however, abandoned in the light of the following observations :

(i) The rate of disproportionation of Tl^{II} ^{34,35} is much larger than the rates of the electron transfer reactions.

(ii) The standard oxidation potential³⁶ of the redox couple Tl^{III}/Tl^I is much larger than that of the Tl^{III}/Tl^{II} redox couple exhibiting Tl^{II} to be a stronger oxidant than Tl^{III} in its redox reactions. There is every possibility that thallium(II) formed in initial interaction remains in solvent cage and reacts with the substrate without diffusing out of the cage. This will also eliminate the chances of formation of substrate free radicals in the reaction as is observed.

Conclusion :

We started exploring kinetics of the title reaction to understand whether or not the reaction occurs via an intermediate complex between oxidant and substrate. We obtained kinetic evidence for such a complex and was indirectly confirmed by the effect of chloride ion. Secondly the transient species thallium(II) is not indicated in absence of any effect of acryic acid on the rate of the reaction.

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